

WIDESPREAD USE OF WALNUT LEAF EXTRACT IN COSMETIC PRODUCTION

¹Baizakova Balnur Saparbek qizi, ²Akramova Rano Ramizitdinovna

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10841183>

¹student of the Department of food and cosmetic-perfume products, Tashkent Institute of Chemical Technology, Republic of Uzbekistan, Tashkent e-mail: klarahaldybaeva@gmail.com

²PhD, professor of the Department Technology of food and cosmetic-perfume products, Tashkent Institute of Chemical Technology Republic of Uzbekistan, Tashkent

Abstract: The article provides for the production of extract and powder from walnut leaves for cosmetic production. The results of obtaining extract and powder from walnut leaves, as well as physic-chemical research and organoleptic indicators of the obtained raw materials are presented. The research results made it possible to develop a cosmetic product based on walnut leaf extract and powder.

Key words: extract, walnut leaf, cosmetic production, powder, composition of the product, essential oil.

Introductions. Development of new cosmetic products is the correct way to obtain natural extracts and selection of the required composition of components that have the specified properties.

In recent years, another mechanism has attracted the attention of scientists (with it associated with the appearance of typical symptoms of skin aging such as wrinkles, sagging, decreased elasticity) - increasing activity of the dermis, destroying the components of the extracellular matrix, including its main structural elements - collagen, elastin. A direct consequence of this is the premature appearance of wrinkles and loss of skin elasticity.

From time immemorial, folk healers have used walnut leaves to treat people. The first mention of walnut leaves is found in the philosopher of the Middle Ages - Avicenna. The healer appreciated the ingredient for the rapid healing of wounds, an antidote to poisoning and dysentery. Avicenna especially noted the hemostatic properties of the leaves.

Walnut leaf extract has unique properties, such as wound healing, antimicrobial, antiviral, anti-inflammatory, and immunostimulant properties. From a medical point of view, the leaves help increase blood clotting and reduce glucose levels, which is very useful for diabetes. They are also useful in helping the body fight viral infections.

Walnut leaf extract is used as an active ingredient in supplements for some purposes, such as supporting heart health. In the food industry, walnut leaf extract can be used as a food additive to impart walnut aroma and flavor to foods, and in aromatherapy, walnut leaf extract can be used to create soothing and relaxing aromas.

The technology of an emulsion-based cosmetic cream with a thick extract of walnut leaves for the care of aging skin. Important indicators that ensure the consumer properties of cosmetic creams are their structural, mechanical and rheological parameters. As a result of experimental studies to study the influence of the ratio of base components on the technological and rheological properties of model bases.

As a result of the research, the composition of a medicinal and cosmetic cream with an extract of walnut leaves of local origin was experimentally substantiated. The introduction of the extract from the leaves into the hydrophilic phase of the cream can be carried out at a temperature of 65°C. The study of the effect of temperature on the structural and mechanical properties of the developed cream was established at the stage of packaging the cream in tubes and should be carried out at a temperature of 40 - 50°C. The experiment also proved the necessity of the cream maturation stage. The reproducibility of analysis methods is confirmed by the results of statistical processing of experimental data. Storage conditions have been established and rational packaging of the medicinal and cosmetic cream has been selected, which ensure its stability for one year of storage. As a result of the studies, the presence of anti-inflammatory, therapeutic, moisturizing effects of the cream, as well as its harmlessness with long-term use, was proven.

Reference:

1. Bandyukova V.A., Oganesyanyan E.T., Lisevetskaya L.I., Sidelnikova V.I., Shinkarenko A.L. Some results of studying the chemical composition of plants in the North Caucasus // Phenolic compounds and their biological functions. M., 1968. pp. 95–100.
2. Shinkarenko A.L., Sokolov S.D., Dorodneva V.I. Chemical and pharmacological study of flavonoids complexes of walnut and black walnut leaves // Issues of balneology, pharmacy, pharmacology. Pyatigorsk, 1967. pp. 365–366.
3. Bandyukova V.A., Shinkarenko A.L., Kazakov A.L. Methods for studying natural flavonoids. Pyatigorsk, 1977. 72 p.
4. Bandyukova V.A. Plant phenolic acids, their esters and glycosides // Chemistry of natural compounds. 1983. No. 3. pp. 263–273.